

PREPOSITIONS

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Abstract: In this paper, the problem of the meaning of the preposition in English is revealed. The interpretation of the term "preposition" is given in detail, as well as the main features of the use of the official part of speech, depending on certain sentences.

Keywords: preposition, service part of speech, sentence, phrase, group, category.

Each part of speech has a specific function, a unique semantic meaning and is involved in the construction of sentences. An equally significant figure in the category of service parts of speech is the preposition. The term "preposition" comes from the Latin " praepositio ", where " prae " means before, and " positus " means put. From this follows the English " preposition " (preposition). What is the definition of this term? A preposition is a functional part of speech that in most cases precedes the noun, but in exceptional cases it can occur behind it. Also, this service part of speech is a special link in the construction of a sentence or phrase between significant parts of speech: verb, noun, adjective, adverb, pronoun. The semantic function of the preposition is location in space.

But if in Russian the preposition is reserved for a single function, semantic, then in English the role of the preposition is divided into two meanings. The first function is the same as in Russian: There are a lot of books on the desk - There are a lot of books on the desk. The second meaning is assigned to the role for finding the case, in contrast to the Russian language, in which the case is determined by the end of the word. In the sentence, considered on the basis of the previous role of the preposition in English, the phrase "a lot of books " is translated into Russian without a preposition, that is, it means "a lot of books."

This means that prepositions are words that reflect certain relationships in a linguistic concept. There are three groups of these prepositions: spatial, temporal, abstract. If in Russian these relations exist due to case endings and prepositions, then in English there are no case endings, and relations are expressed using only prepositions.

A short, simplified definition of a preposition is a service part of speech that carries relationships between the members of a sentence. In other words, prepositions have a function in constructing sentences. The origin of this type of service part of speech comes from the roots of words of ancient origin. It is wrong to assume that prepositions are a closed,

unchangeable group. Their renewal and increase in number is extremely rare, and comes from significant or independent parts of speech. Basically, prepositions are replenished due to participles: during, considering ; there are also compound forms of prepositions from words deprived of their original meaning with the preposition: owing to .

The abstract nature of the transfer of relations by prepositions prompted the allocation of such service parts of speech into a separate group of " grammaticalized ", which had a long existence. This group of prepositions was similar to cases in other languages, and therefore these parts of speech were not translated literally. This type of prepositions includes of , with , to , by . A feature of abstract prepositions is the transformation into spatial prepositions and vice versa. A good example is the preposition " by ", which has a double meaning, both a display in space and the use of a means, a tool: to stay by wall ; he was invited by his sister .

According to the degree of complexity, there are three groups of prepositions: simple, complex, participial.

The prepositions of the first group originated by combining with a verb or noun, the origin of this group dates back to the Old English period. These are the prepositions at , under , on .

The second group appeared due to the expression of relations associated with space and action: inside , underneath , upon .

Participle prepositions appeared due to the reduction of subordinate clauses sentences in which the predicate turned into a participle, and the subordinate clauses turned into prepositions: during , past , except .

Meaning functions divides prepositions into several more categories. Prepositions indicating the place, location of objects, persons: behind - behind, behind; under - under; over - over; near , by - about, near. Prepositions showing directions: into - in; up - up; down - down; to the left - left, to the right - to the right. Temporary : by - to some point; till - before; before - after; past - past. Prepositions of reason: thanks to - thanks; because of - because of , because, since.

A preposition is an integral unit of any language, especially in English linguistics. Despite the fact that this part of speech is auxiliary, it carries out important functions in establishing a semantic connection in phrases and sentences between independent parts of speech, even affecting their lexical meaning.

Literature:

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